

MEDICAL SCIENCES

LUNG MACROPHAGES: HISTOLOGICAL, IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL AND ELECTRON MICROSCOPIC STUDY

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Abstract

Lung macrophages (LMs) play a crucial role in immune defense reactions in the lungs. However, data on the genesis, taxonomic composition, histotopography, immunohistochemical and electron microscopic parameters of LM in white rats are still contradictory. The aim of the study was to study histologically, immunohistochemically and electron microscopically the population of macrophages in normal (intact) lungs of white rats. For the study, 22 healthy intact white rats of an unknown breeding line weighing 200-250 g were selected, kept on the same food and water under standard vivarium conditions. Histological, immunohistochemical, transmission-electron-microscopic and morphometric analyzes were performed on lung pieces, quantitative indicators were processed statistically. It was found that macrophages account for 3.0-13.0% (8.8±1.0%) of the total cell content in the lungs of white rats. We identified 3 subpopulations of LM: 1) alveolar, 2) interstitial-BALT and 3) bronchial. The belonging of macrophages to the air-blood barrier should be clarified. Immunohistochemically, LM is a heteromorphic and heterogeneous population. Individual immunohistochemical and ultrastructural polymorphism may be associated with the functional purpose and degree of activity of a particular macrophage. Contacts of macrophages with other structural elements of the lungs are directly related to the migration ability, functional activity, and the specificity of the phase of the expulsion of these cells. The results obtained can be used as the basis for interpreting the actual experimental data.

Keywords: lung macrophages; immunohistochemistry, ultrastructure, rat.

Actuality. Lung macrophages (LM) have a crucial role in the secretion and reception of immunomodulators and the implementation of immune defense responses in the respiratory system. However, data on the genesis, taxonomic composition, histotopography, quantification and functional significance of the LM population in humans and small animals used in experiments are still conflicting [1, 2, 3, 4]. In organ-tissue sections of the lungs, their cellular composition, histotopography, immunohistochemical and electron-microscopic properties, location density, morphometric indicators, as well as their relationships with other constituents in the bronchi, alveoli, vessel wall, and interstitial areas have not been adequately investigated. The relationship between the morphological characteristics of these cells and their functional purpose is not completely sharp [2, 4, 5, 6]. The listed aspects make it difficult to objectively evaluate the determination of lung macrophages, their specific activity in normal and different pathological conditions, and it is necessary to carry out appropriate complex research.

The purpose of the study. Considering the above, the aim of the present research was to study the histological, immunohistochemical, ultrastructural and morphometric characteristics of macrophage population in normal (intact) white rat lungs.

Materials and methods. The object of study were selected the 22 healthy intact male white rats of outbreeding line, weighing 200-250 grams, kept in the same food and water supply under standard vivarium

conditions. After anesthesia with intra-abdominal injection of ketamine the animals were became lifeless by decapitation. During the research, the requirements of the European Union Convention on the rules of behavior with vertebrate experimental animals were strictly complied [7, 8]. The tissue samples were taken from 4 lobes in the right lung, also samples from the left lung were taken around the portal and peripheral zone. For histological and immunohistochemical analysis, the samples were fixed in 4.0% buffered formalin, as well as for electron microscopic analysis fixed in solution contains buffered 2.5% glutaraldehyde + 2% paraformaldehyde + 4% glucose + 0.1% picric acid. The obtained sections of paraffin blocks with thickness 4.0-5.0 µm were processed by histological and immunohistochemical methods. For general histological research were used the hematoxylin-eosin and picrofuchsin-hematoxylin staining. Macrophages were determined by staining with 0.1% trypan acid, 0.05% buffered thionine, and immunohistochemical reactions with CD68, CD163, CD207 (langerin), CD1a, S100 protein, vimentin, and Granzyme B antibodies. Parallel serial sections were also stained with "Epithelial Membrane Antigen (EMA)" monoclonal antibodies.

The semithin sections of Araldite-epon blocks (thickness 0.5-1.0 µm) were stained by double staining (solution "A" - 0.5% methylene blue, 0.5% azur-II, 0.5% bura and "B" solution - 5% alcohol, 0.1% basic fuchsin) [9]. Then, the areas of the blocks to be studied were marked, and their ultrathin sections (thickness 50-

60 nm) were first stained with 2.0% uranyl acetate, then with 0.6% pure lead citrate prepared in a 0.1N solution of NaOH.

Studies at the light optical level were performed in the stereometric mode on the Axio Scope A14 (Carl Zeiss) microscope with the AxioCam ERc5s video camera, and the ultrastructural analysis was performed on the contrasted ultrathin sections at 80.0 kV on the JEM-1400 transmission electron microscope (Japan). In the technical performance of histological, immunohistochemical and electron-microscopic analyzes and the interpretation of their results were used generally accepted instructions [10, 11, 12]. In the quantitative analysis, the average mathematical value of the indicators and its average error ($M \pm m$) were calculated at the confidence level of $P=0.95$ ($p < 0.05$) [13].

Figure 1. The amount of macrophages (in percentage) within cell composition making up the lungs of white rat. Explanation given in text.

Histological features. The macrophages belonging to all 3 subpopulations have acidophilic cytoplasm and lobulated nucleus in histological staining of paraffin block sections; it is stained with variable intensity by trypan acid and thionine. They are fuchsin-negative in semithin sections of araldite-epon blocks; they distinguished from the surrounding cells with hypochrome cytoplasm and a pale relatively large nucleus. Although interstitial macrophages are located individually, but they created different contacts with the stromal elements of the organ and the wall of the vessels there. Macrophages within BALT are chaotically scattered individually and accumulated in relatively numerous microislets consisting of 2-4 cells. We assume that macrophages in BALT aggregates can be composed of both free (motile) and fixed (immobile) functional groups due to their migratory ability. So, it is possible for some of them to migrate both to interstitial areas and into the bronchial wall (intramural

Research results. Analogous results were obtained in both lungs of white rats. Macrophages make up $8.8 \pm 1.0\%$ of the total cell composition of the organ (min - 3.0%; max - 13.0%; Fig. 1). Although certain differences were found in the right and left lung on this parameter, they are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). At the same time, macrophages are more common in both lungs, especially on the left, in the periportal and central zones. Histotopographically, we distinguished 3 subpopulations of lung macrophages: 1) alveolar ($44.2 \pm 4.2\%$), 2) interstitial - BALT ($41.0 \pm 4.2\%$) and 3) bronchial ($14.8 \pm 1.3\%$; Fig. 2). It should be noted that intravascular (flow-through) macrophages were not detected due to the methodological features of of the present study.

Figure 2. The amount of macrophages (in percentage) regarding to histotopographic subpopulations within white rat lungs. Explanation given in text.

layers). This may be the case at least for free (migrating) macrophages. We supposed that dendritic macrophages of the BALT are located in specific microzones in an immobile, fixed characteristic as local "antigen-presenting cells". In histological sections, alveolar and bronchial macrophages are located individually and do not form any aggregates and complexes, but are observed both on the surface and inside the epithelial lining (layer) (Fig. 3).

It should be noted that our conclusions about the genesis and functional characteristics of different morphological types of alveolar macrophages are compatible with the results of some other studies [1, 2, 4, 5].

However, issues related to genesis and functions require more fundamental, systematic research. General histologically were found the certain relationships between the shape, size of macrophages and their localization.

Figure 3. Histological characteristics of macrophages (shown by red arrow) in white rat lungs. A - interstitial (stromal) macrophages; perivascular and interstitial localization in the subcapsular stroma; right lung, peripheral zone. B – macrophages in the lumen of alveoli and aero-hematic barrier; left lung, central zone. C - macrophages in the periglandular stroma in the bronchial wall; right lung, main bronchus wall in the portal zone. D - macrophages in the peribronchiolar BALT collection; left lung, periportal zone. A, B, C – paraffin blocks, D – araldite-epon block. Stain: A, B - hematoxylin-eosin; C - 0.05% buffered thionine; D - methylene blue - basic fuchsin. Magnification: A – x250; B, C, D - x480.

Thus, the $53.5 \pm 5.8\%$ of bronchial and interstitial-BALT macrophages have one or more protrusions of different sizes. However, the majority of macrophages in alveolar lumen ($86.0 \pm 8.2\%$) are oval or round in shape, no have protrusions or pseudopods. The relative smoothness of the surface of alveolar macrophages

leads to the lack of direct contacts with the neighboring structural elements of the organ. Taking into account that this aspect makes it much easier for macrophages to move freely in the alveolar space and migrate to the airways; we have expressed our opinion about this in our previous study [14, 15].

Figure 4. Immunohistochemical characteristics of macrophages (shown by red arrow) in white rat lungs. A - alveolar macrophages; CD68 positivity and pigmentophagia; left lung, central zone. B – macrophages in BAL collection, right lung, central zone; CD207 (Langerin) positivity; BALT around the main bronchus on right lung, portal zone. C - interstitial-BALT macrophages; CD68 positivity and pigmentophagia; right lung, peripheral zone. D - interstitial macrophages; CD1 α positivity; polymorphism on shape and size; close contacts with stromal, lymphoid cells and vessels; left lung, periportal zone. Stain: immunohistochemical reaction with CD68 in A, C; with CD207 (Langerin) in B; with CD1 α monoclonal antibodies in D. Magnification: A - x480; Scale bar: B, C - 50 μ m, D - 20 μ m

In stereometric analysis, the largest macrophages by size observed in the alveoli. In the sections the diameter of the alveolar macrophages is $13.6 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$, in the bronchi - the length is $10.7 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{m}$ and the width is $5.7 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{m}$; and the average width in interstitial areas was $12.2 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$.

Immunohistochemical features. In all 3 subpopulations of lung macrophages, "EMA" is negative (-; 100.0%), and vimentin is positive (+; 100.0%). In parallel with vimentin, total positivity was recorded with CD68 and Iba-1 (AIF-1) (100.0%). However, the positivity/negativity pointer of other markers are variable (Fig. 4; Table 1). The first results of the correlation analysis show that the location (histotopography) of macrophage selectively have a statistically reliable relationship with some immunohistochemical markers. For example, the macrophages that localized in the interstitial areas, BALT deposits and bronchial epithelium demonstrated

in parallel with the universal "vimentin+/CD68+" characteristic the status "CD1 α + /CD207+ /S100+". Also the macrophages within alveoli have the status "granzyme B+ /CD163+". There is a high possibility of a direct correlation the status "CD163+" with the localization of specific types of macrophages in alveoli, bronchial epithelial lining, bronchial wall and BALT collections. However, possible relationships between immunohistochemical status and macrophage histotopography are complex, not fully studied in the present study, and require separate investigation. We assume that the "vimentin+/CD68+" status of macrophages in all 3 subpopulations is conditioned by their genetic identity. The found histotopographical individual immunohistochemical polymorphism is probably determined by the functional purpose and degree of activity of a specific macrophage; but for the clarification of this provision, it is necessary to conduct more fundamental and complex researches [14].

Table 1.

Immunohistochemical marker	Subpopulation of lung macrophages		
	Alveolar	Interstitial - BALT	Bronchial
EMA	- (100,0%)	- (100,0%)	- (100,0%)
Vimentin	+ (100,0%)	+ (100,0%)	+ (100,0%)
CD68	+ (100,0%)	+ (100,0%)	+ (100,0%)
CD1 α	+ (9,0%) - (91,0%)	+ (86,6%) - (13,4%)	+ (31,0%) - (69,0%)
S100 protein	+ (11,6%) - (88,4%)	+ (94,8%) - (5,2%)	+ (92,4%) - (7,6%)
CD207 (Langerin)	+ (7,7%) - (92,3%)	+ (92,7%) - (7,3%)	+ (88,0%) - (12,0%)
Granzyme B	+ (93,3%) - (6,7%)	+ (47,2%) - (52,8%)	+ (9,1%) - (90,9%)
CD163	+ (76,5%) - (23,5%)	+ (44,5%) - (54,5%)	+ (82,2%) - (17,8%)

Note: "+" - amount of positive macrophages (%); "-" - amount of negative macrophages (%)

Ultrastructural features. In the electron-microscopic identification of lung macrophages, we used the following ultrastructural signs as a basis: roughness of plasmalemmal surface with one or more number of pseudopods; the simplicity and small amount of contacts with other cells; the shape of nucleus; the specific appearance of condensed (dense)

and scattered (dispersed) chromatin; relatively numerous phagolysosomes and residual bodies; in pale matrix cytoplasm the chaotically scattered osmiophilic and crystalloid deposits, network of several polysomes, tubules and cisternae; a few number of small spherical and oval shaped mitochondria with an electron dense matrix and sparsely scattered cytoskeletal filaments.

Figure 5. Ultrastructural characteristics of macrophages in white rat lungs. A - localization in the alveolar epithelial lining and aero-hematic barrier. B - nucleus with characteristic shape and characteristic chromatin content. C - few tubules, mitochondria (blue arrow), phagolysosomes (yellow arrow), residual bodies (red arrow), sparse cytoskeletal elements. D - many small sized osmiophilic and relatively coarse crystalloid deposits scattered diffusely in the cytoplasm. Scale bar: A 5 μ m; B 2 μ m; C and D 500nm.

In addition, there are pigment microgranules and conglomerates in the cells of all 3 subpopulations, also lipid/lipoid droplets in some macrophages in the lumen of alveoli, and a variable number of pinocytosis vesicles in the macrophages contacting the capillary wall (Fig. 5).

Conclusion. Summarising above data the lung macrophages comprise 3.0–13.0% ($8.8 \pm 1.0\%$) of the total cell content of the organ in white rat. Histotopographically, 3 subpopulations of macrophages can be distinguished: 1) alveolar, 2) interstitial-BALT and 3) bronchial. Also, the affiliation of macrophages that present in aero-hematic barrier should be specified [14,15]. Although the lung macrophages are immunohistochemically distinguished by universal cytospecific markers, they are actually a heteromorphic and heterogeneous population. Individual immunohistochemical and ultrastructural polymorphism can be related to the functional purpose and degree of activity of a particular macrophage. The contacts of macrophages with other structural elements of the lungs are directly related to their migration ability, functional activity and specific phase of displacement processes of those cells. The obtained results can be used as a basis for the interpretation of the actual data of the experiments devoted to the pathology of the lungs and bronchi.

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